

Differential effects of cryo-concentration on volatiles in apple juice

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Abstract

Cryo-concentration of apple juice shows that concentration of esters increases proportionally with increasing Brix value while the concentration of furan compounds has an irregular but in some cases close to exponential increase during the concentration process. Some furans have pleasant caramel-like odours, which have been reported in apple wine from cryo-concentrated apple juice. It is therefore concluded that cryo-concentration introduces an opportunity to produce richer apple wine not just due to concentration but most likely also due to formation of pleasantly smelling aroma compounds such as furans.

Keywords: cryo-concentration, furans, fruit wine, de novo synthesis

Introduction

New ways of utilizing Danish apples are of interest in order to prevent food waste and loss of this Danish cultural heritage [1]. In earlier projects conducted by University of Copenhagen in collaboration with Cold Hand Winery (Randers, Denmark) it was found that several apple cultivars produced in Denmark are highly suitable for wine production [2]. However, due to the low sugar content of plain apple juice, regular wine of good quality, as known from grapes, is difficult to achieve. To prepare an apple juice, which is more suitable for wine production, cryo-concentration of the juice prior to fermentation can be done [3]. Cryo-concentration is a gentle process where sugars, acids and volatiles are efficiently concentrated with low losses of both volatiles and solids. The concentrated juice – and the wine produced from it – is generally intensified. However, it has been an experience that the cryo-concentration does not equally affect all volatiles. This study shows the differential effects of cryo-concentration on two groups of aroma compounds: esters and furans in apple juice made from ‘Bramley’ and ‘Graasten’ cultivars.

Experimental

Materials

Apple juice was freshly prepared from ‘Graasten’ (90%) and ‘Bramley’ (10%) cultivars harvested at the Pometum, which is University of Copenhagen’s orchard.

Method

Juice was frozen at -18°C in two 10L plastic containers (A and B) and kept frozen for four months. The juice was thawed slowly (at 0.0 ± 0.5°C for five days) following the method of complete block cryo-concentration inspired by Aider & Hallux [3] (Figure 1). Samples (n=17) of individual thawed fractions were collected throughout the melting process and content of soluble solids was measured as °Brix. Volatile profile was analysed by dynamic headspace sampling (DHS) and gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) as described in [4]. The objective was to measure juice composition at approximately every 200 mL of thawed must. A control was thawed completely over six days at 5°C.

Figure 1: Left: frozen apple juice before thawing. Right: remaining ice block with little dry matter left after thawing.

Results and discussion

During thawing, °Brix decreased from 49 in the first fraction to 9 in the last, when collection was terminated. By DHS-GC-MS analysis, a total of 88 volatiles were identified reflecting the common composition found in apples: esters (n=27), alcohols (n=15), aldehydes (n=15), acids (n=11), furans (n=8), ketones (n=7), and terpenes (n=5).

Esters

Figure 2 illustrates how the concentration of esters was proportional to Brix values, thus the concentrations followed a linear tendency with R^2 close to 1. This development in volatile compounds is anticipated upon cryo-concentration and indicates that esters are concentrated and not lost nor formed during the thawing process.

Figure 2: Concentration of esters in thawed fractions with different °Brix. The plot includes all measurements from container A and B.

Furans

High Brix samples of cryo-concentrated apple juice also contained high concentrations of furans. The development was, however, very irregular and it was not possible to fit a common model to all samples. If data from the two biological replicates (A and B) were analysed separately, it appeared that they behaved very differently. Figure 3 shows data for three furans in container B, and here the development was well described by power functions. The development in container A could not be described by power functions or any other standard

functions. It should be noted, that container A and B were treated the same way, and that data for the esters (Figure 2) showed identical patterns in the two containers.

Comparison of the development in concentrations of esters and furans shows that the increase in furans is not only due to the concentration effect. Furans are possibly also formed de novo during cryo-concentration.

Figure 3: Concentration of furans in thawed fractions with different °Brix. The plot includes only measurements from container B.

Microenvironments and acid-catalysed caramelisation

The formation of furans is often associated with heat treatment. However, even at low temperatures, the reaction mechanisms of caramelisation can be considered identical to those at high heat, if the sugar solution is very concentrated and the pH is low [5]. In the present study, pH varied from 3.37 in the most concentrated fractions to 3.52 in the least concentrated.

During cryo-concentration, high concentrations of solids, such as sugars and acids are achieved. As the freezing point decreases with high concentrations of these compounds, a part of the juice will remain unfrozen even at temperatures below -7°C [6], which provides the opportunity of microenvironments to arise, which is favourable for the formation of furans by caramelisation reactions. It can be hypothesised that these microenvironments are a part of the reason for formation of furans as well as the reason for irregularity of formation.

Formation of furans during storage of cryo-concentrated apple juice

A sample of cryo-concentrated apple juice (19.5°Brix) was kept stored at 0°C for 14 days. This was done in order to investigate whether the high sugar and acid levels in the cryo-concentrated apple juice can lead to formation of aroma compounds during storage. Compared to the control, cryo-concentrated juice had 27% higher level of total furans while stored cryo-concentrated juice had 71% more. The samples of cryo-concentrated juice and stored cryo-concentrated juice had the same °Brix (19.5°Brix). The difference between these two samples was 35% which indicates a tendency that storage of the cryo-concentrated apple juice results in formation of furans. The increase was primarily due to 2-furanmethanol, 5-ethyl-2(5H)-furanone, 2(5H)-furanone and furfural. This supports the hypothesis that microenvironments with high sugar/acid concentrations might enable formation of furans. Due to lack of replicates, significance testing could not be performed. Nonetheless, a three-fold increase was seen for 2-furanmethanol in stored samples compared to non-stored.

Tadao Kurata and Yosito Sakurai [7] found that ascorbic acid degrades to furfural under acidic conditions during storage or cooking of foods (Figure 4). It is hypothesised that this could be part of the reason for the increase in furans after storage of the cryo-concentrated apple juice.

Figure 4: Degradation reaction of ascorbic acid to furfural under acidic conditions.

Conclusion

Cryo-concentration of apple juice affects volatiles such as furans and esters in different ways. While esters were found to concentrate proportionally to °Brix, furans had a different and very irregular development during the concentration process, most probably due to de novo synthesis even at the low temperatures applied. This finding supports previous findings from University of Copenhagen where a higher level of furans was found in cryo-concentrated sparkling apple wine compared to non-cryo-concentrated apple wine. It is therefore concluded that cryo-concentration introduces an opportunity to produce richer apple wine not just due to a general concentration of the soluble solids but most likely also due to formation of new aroma compounds with caramel-like or other pleasantly smelling qualities. This presents an innovative way of using surplus apples as well as specially produced high quality apples, and could lead to new and interesting products from local produce with a sensory profile, which differentiates them from other apple products.

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